

SIMONS FOUNDATION

The Ptolemy project

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The Ptolemy collaboration

The cosmological neutrino background

- ▶ Messengers from **1s** after the Big Bang
- ▶ **Cold Matter** ($T \sim 1.9\text{K}$)
- ▶ About **100/cm³** here and now
- ▶ Faint kinetic energy ($< \text{eV}$)

The Ptolemy
project

M.G. Betti et al JCAP07 (2019) 047

A novel **compact** spectrometer concept

The Ptolemy concept

- ▶ Precisely defined (ppm) voltage difference: β electron slowed down - and removed - to decimate the flux.
- ▶ Measure a $\sim 1-10$ eV electron with $10^{-2} - 10^{-3}$ resolution

The target, atomic tritium ${}^3\text{H}$

JCAP 06(2007)015

Weinberg, Phys Rev 128, 1457–1473 (1962).

Neutrino capture on Tritium

M.G.Betti et al, JCAP 07 (2019) 047

- ▶ Need 100g ${}^3\text{H}$ for few CnB events/y

First step is to measure neutrino mass from the endpoint

The Ptolemy ingredients

- ▶ Tritium on **graphene**:
atomic ^3H stored on a thin electrode
- ▶ Fast ~ 30 GHz radiation detection as *trigger*
- cyclotron radiation emission (CRES - see Project-8)
- ▶ **Novel electromagnetic filter** M.G.Betti et al,
Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics,
106, (2019) 120-131
- ▶ Hemispherical electrostatic analyser
 - ▶ *In future* cryogenic **micro-calorimeter** based on
Transition Edge Sensors (**TES**)

Towards tritiated graphene

- ▶ Thin graphene as initial electrodes (hold tritium atom at well defined potential)

Record 90% hydrogen coverage for graphene

Stability in vacuum at room T

Carbon 1s line shape from X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

Nano Lett. 2022, 22, 7, 2971–2977

Accepted in App. Surf. Sc.

Transparency measurement on-going

Our method here: *Carbon*, 216 (2024) 118502

The demonstrator

- ▶ Custom magnet with a specially **shaped fringe field** (exponentially falling B field)
- ▶ Combined with **gradient** electric field

Apponi et al, JINST 17 (2022) 05, P05021

M.Farino et al, JINST 20 (2025) 08, P08025

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2512.19437>

The gradient B field

- ★ Uniform region:
~ 10 x 10 x 80 cm
- ★ $\Delta B/B$ (1T) ~ 10^{-4}

- ▶ Superconducting magnet
(being produced by ASG, Genoa, IT)
- ▶ To be delivered to INFN LNGS in 2026

The filtering principle: drift velocity

- ▶ While electrons are (fast) spiralling around B field lines they are “guided” with “macroscopic” velocity $\mathbf{V}_d = \mathbf{V}_E + \mathbf{V}_B$

The filtering

- ▶ Only electron with the desired energy propagate to the end of the filter

- ▶ Kinetic energy K drained in favour of potential energy

$$\frac{dK_{\perp}}{dt} = e\vec{E} \cdot \vec{V}_d$$

CREs at LNGS

- ▶ **Electron trap:** waveguide with electrodes in magnetic field to study cyclotron radiation from ^{83m}Kr
- ▶ Develop technologies to detect CRE in a **very short time**
 - ▶ Early *trigger* to set-up the filter electrodes

Full simulation

- ▶ Based on COMSOL, CST, Kassiopeia,...
- ▶ Aiming at maximising efficiency for a given pitch angle
 - ▶ Dynamic filter will be tuned on-line (using CRES)

Final electron analyser

- ▶ Electrons with $E_p \sim 10\text{-}100$ eV are propagating within hemispherical electrodes.

**Routinely used in
synchrotron beam lines
for condensed matter
physics experiments**

- ▶ **Position** at the end mapped to **energy** (MCP with fine readout)
- ▶ **10 meV** energy resolution well possible

Detection with cryo-micro-calorimeters

- ▶ Transition Edge Sensors (TES) technology
 - ▶ Developed for photon sensing
 - ▶ Increase in **temperature** measures **deposited energy**

C: thermal capacitance
G: thermal conductance

$$\Delta E \approx (k_B T^2 C B)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Energy resolution: better at low T and small C

Detection of electrons with TES

- ▶ Electron absorption mechanism **very** different from photons at 10-100 eV.

- ▶ Developed an **electron cold source** in a cryostat (based on field emitting **carbon nanotubes**)

C. Pepe et al, PR App 22.4 (2024) L041007

First demonstration electron and photon TES energy resolution is the same

Sensitivity to neutrino mass

- ▶ If demonstrated, the Ptolemy concept can then be used for a neutrino mass measurement with a 1-100 μg tritium mass

End point **theoretical systematic**
(tritium bond to graphene)
included

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2504.13259>

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Apponi et al Phys. Rev. D
106, 053002

Conclusion and outlook

- ▶ Ptolemy project aims at developing a novel small scale spectrometer for a future CvB detection
- ▶ A first step will be to measure the endpoint of tritium and make a competitive **neutrino mass** measurement
- ▶ **Filter demonstrator** being assembled in **2026** at INFN **LNGS**
 - ▶ First results from other prototypes coming soon
 - ▶ *A neutrino mass experiment being proposed afterwards*
- ▶ **Feasibility** study to port **graphene hydrogenation** to **tritium**: now working with **UK AEA** at AGHS for JET at Culham.
 - ▶ **Many advances in critical aspects** (low energy electron detection, graphene characterisations, theoretical uncertainty evaluation, high voltage measurement & monitoring,...)

